

Oxobridged Dimeric Complexes of Hydrazones

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Acid hydrazides and their hydrazones have been reported to possess tuberculostatic activity and researches in this field culminated interest to many investigators till recent years^{1,2}. The present investigation is in continuation of the work on metal chelates of acid hydrazones of potential biological interest and describes the synthesis of *p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde salicylic acid hydrazone (HBSH,L) and 3-hydroxy-4-methoxybenzaldehyde salicylic acid hydrazone (HMBSH,L') and their dimeric chelates with Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II}.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data of the chelates (Table 1) are in accordance with the general formula (ML₂.2H₂O)₂, where M=bipositive metal ion and L=C₁₄H₁₀N₂O₃ or C₁₅H₁₃N₂O₄.

In HBSH, keto-enol tautomerism can be visualised in solution owing to the presence of one proton nitrogen in α -position to the keto group.

In HBSH, bands at 3 475 (OH)³, 3 380 and 3 240 (NH)⁴ and 1 760 cm⁻¹ (C=O) are observed, which suggest that the ligand exists in keto form. These bands are absent in all the complexes and instead new bands appear at 1 665–1 645 (C=N) and 1 605–1 600 cm⁻¹ (C=N–N=C). This suggests that coordination occurs in the enolic form of the ligand. A shift in ν_{C-O} band by 10–20 cm⁻¹ indicates the formation of phenolic oxygen bridge in the complexes⁶⁻⁹. A positive shift in the ν_{C-O} band indicates the presence of phenolic oxygen bridge. Formation of oxobridge is also suggested by the appearance of a new band at 760–750 cm⁻¹ in the complexes⁷.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA AND LIGAND FIELD PARAMETERS OF COMPLEXES

Compd./ (Colour)	Analyses % : Found/Calcd.)				μ_e^{if} B.M.	10Dq cm ⁻¹	B' cm ⁻¹	β	β^0 %	ν_2 cm ⁻¹	ν_2/ν_1	σ_1/σ_2
	Metal	C	H	N								
(CoL.2H ₂ O) ₂ (Brown)	16.88 (16.62)	48.15 (47.95)	4.01 (4.0)	8.02 (7.98)	4.62	11 600	905	0.932	6.8	22 016	2.11	—
(NiL.2H ₂ O) ₂ (Reddish brown)	16.81 (16.60)	48.19 (47.97)	4.01 (4.0)	8.03 (7.99)	2.76	11 752	970	0.918	8.2	17 141	1.62	—
(CuL.2H ₂ O) ₂ (Brown)	17.94 (17.70)	47.50 (47.2)	3.96 (3.85)	7.92 (7.82)	1.47	12 163	—	—	—	—	—	1.46
(CoL'.2H ₂ O) ₂ (Brown)	15.50 (15.45)	47.50 (47.27)	4.22 (4.08)	7.38 (7.20)	4.58	11 540	924	0.951	4.8	21 744	2.12	—
(NiL'.2H ₂ O) ₂ (Orange)	15.47 (15.25)	47.54 (47.25)	4.22 (4.08)	7.39 (7.20)	2.90	10 869	963	0.912	8.56	17 646	1.60	—
(CuL'.2H ₂ O) ₂ (Grey)	16.53 (16.32)	46.94 (46.54)	4.17 (4.05)	7.30 (7.10)	1.52	12 086	—	—	—	—	—	1.45

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The C=N stretching frequency at 1680 cm^{-1} in the ligand HBSH shifts towards lower side by $40\text{--}30\text{ cm}^{-1}$, indicating the involvement of azomethine nitrogen in the complex formation^{6,11,12}. The negative shift in C=N stretching is due to the change in bond order of C=N after the bonding of nitrogen with the metal. A second new band due to $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ is observed at $1655\text{--}1645\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which may be a composite band due to $(\nu_{\text{O=C=N}} + \nu_{\text{C=N}})$. The shifting of $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ band at 1535 cm^{-1} in the ligand by $15\text{--}10\text{ cm}^{-1}$ suggests involvement of phenolic oxygen in coordination. However, the new band at $1310\text{--}1300\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the complexes may be attributed to $\nu_{\text{C=O-M}}$ enolic. The band at 3475 cm^{-1} (CH) in the ligand disappears in all the complexes, which further supports the above statement. The shifting of N-N stretching band at 1020 cm^{-1} in the ligand to higher frequency by 25 cm^{-1} in the complexes, indicates the monodentate linking¹³ of $>\text{N-N}<$. The M-O enolic, M-N and M-O phenolic stretching frequencies observed at $535\text{--}530$, $450\text{--}445$ and $410\text{--}400\text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively, in the complexes are well within the assigned range¹⁴, supporting the coordination through oxygen and nitrogen donor atoms. The presence of water molecules within the coordination sphere in the complexes is confirmed by the appearance of three bands in appropriate region. Similar results were obtained for the complexes formed by HMBSH. Additional bands were observed in the case of HMBSH and its metal complexes at 1020 cm^{-1} due to the presence of methoxy group⁹.

The loss of weight at $100\text{--}270^\circ$ in the HBSH and at $100\text{--}270^\circ$ in the HMBSH complexes corresponds to the loss of two molecules of water. Elimination of water at such a high temperature confirms its presence in the coordination sphere of the metal. The decomposition of the complexes starts at $220\text{--}270^\circ$ and the residue on heating upto 800° does not exactly correspond to any definite composition though the constancy in weight is attained.

The magnetic moment values are found to be lower than expected value for octahedral complexes specially in case of the Cu^{II} complex (Table 1). This seems to be due to the binuclear dimeric nature of the complexes^{15,16} and due to Cu-Cu interactions in these oxobridged species. Similar observation was made by Ali and Bose¹⁷ for binuclear complex $[\text{Cu}(\text{ONS})_2]$ which was found to possess an anomalously low magnetic moment value and was thought to be due to the presence of antiferromagnetic interactions between a pair of copper atoms. The magnetic moment and various ligand field parameters are presented in Table 1. DRS studies show three absorption bands each in the Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes and two spin-allowed transition bands in the case of the Co^{II} complexes. The transition corresponding to ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g} (F)$ is not observed as it is weak in nature and is obscured by a high intensity ligand band. Moreover, ν_2 transition is a two-electron process and is thus

weaker by a factor 10^{-2} than the other transitions¹⁸. The values of ν_2/ν_1 or σ_1/σ_2 also support the octahedral geometry of the metal complexes.

It is thus evidenced that each metal ion is coordinated with two phenolic oxygen and one enolic oxygen forming two oxygen bridges. The complex molecule is linked with one azomethine nitrogen donor atom and two water molecules, leading to the formation of dimeric complexes involving octahedral geometry.

Experimental

Salicylic acid hydrazide was prepared and purified by crystallisation in ethanol. All other chemicals were of analytical grade. The physicochemical methods employed are the same as described earlier¹².

Synthesis of ligands: A mixture of *p*-hydroxy- or 3-hydroxy-4-methoxybenzaldehyde and salicylic acid hydrazide (in equimolar ratio) in ethanolic medium, was refluxed over a water-bath for 3 h. It was then cooled to room temperature and the resulting solid was washed with ethanol and petroleum ether and dried over calcium chloride under reduced pressure: HBSH (85%), m.p. 225° ; HMBSH (80%), m.p. 226° . The compounds were found soluble in hot ethanol.

Synthesis of complexes: To a mixture of the metal acetate (0.002 mol) solution (prepared in a minimum amount of water) and ethanol, was added the respective hydrazone (0.004 mol) solution in hot EtOH. The mixture was refluxed on a sand-bath for 2-4 h as necessary in different cases. The Ni^{II} -HBSH and Cu -HMBSH complexes were obtained as coloured solids within 30 min and dried over CaCl_2 under reduced pressure.

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